

MEDICAL SCIENCES

MULTICENTRIC RECURRENT KERATOACANTHOMA AND VERRUCCOUS CARCINOMA

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ABSTRACT

Keratoacanthoma and verrucous carcinoma are low-grade squamous lesions that most often clinically present as difficult to heal verrucous formations. The similarity in the morphology of these pathological processes also creates difficulties in biopsy diagnosis, especially in incisional biopsies and fragmented material. We report a case of an 82-year-old man with multicentric recurrent malignant tumors of the skin. The patient was operated on twice in the surgical department of the Svilengrad Hospital. In 2022, a warty formation was removed from the capillicium, diagnosed biopsy as keratoacanthoma, and from the auricle, near the external auditory canal, an ulcerated area was removed, with a microscopic diagnosis of verrucous carcinoma. In 2025, a second operation was performed due to recurrence of the tumor processes in the same areas. The biopsy examination confirmed the diagnoses of the two primary tumors. An analysis and comparison of verrucous carcinoma and keratoacanthoma is performed. The similarities and differences between these two tumors, the reasons for the difficulties in morphological diagnosis, and a proposal for adding a new cytological criterion for their differentiation are discussed.

Keywords: Cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma; Skin cancer; Keratoacanthoma; Verrucous carcinoma.

Introduction

Multicentric tumors are two or more different malignant tumors in a single patient, arising in different areas of a single organ, often separated by normal tissue. Verrucous lesions on the scalp and maxillofacial region may hide different nosological entities, ranging from benign formations such as seborrheic keratosis, verruca vulgaris, lichen planus, hypertrophic forms of discoid lupus, molluscum contagiosum, to premalignant and malignant conditions such as verrucous carcinoma, squamous carcinoma, even large cell lymphomas and achromatic melanomas [2]. Morphological differentiation of these lesions often creates serious diagnostic difficulties, especially in cases of malignant tumor processes with nested structure.

Keratoacanthoma was first described by Sir Jonathan Hutchinson in 1888, but its epidemiology, diagnostic criteria, prognosis, and treatment guidelines remain controversial to this day. Keratoacanthoma is most commonly described as a rapidly growing, low-grade skin tumor that clinically and histologically mimics well differentiated squamous cell carcinoma. Keratoacanthoma often undergoes spontaneous regression. In these cases, the tumor progresses through 3 stages of development: proliferative, mature, and involutinal. Its occurrence on the scalp is rare and can pose a diagnostic challenge [1].

Verrucous carcinoma is considered a low-grade subtype of squamous cell carcinoma, with cutaneous and mucosal localization. It is characterized by slow growth and may be diagnosed late due to vague histo-

pathological features and mimicking reactive processes. Verrucous carcinoma of the oral cavity and the mobile tongue is sometimes referred to by the historical term “Ackerman tumor,” which is not recommended by the 5th edition of the World Health Organization (WHO). Caution is required when diagnosing verrucous carcinoma, especially in superficial or fragmented biopsies [11].

Case report

From the anamnesis: An 83 year old man was admitted to the Surgery Department of the Svilengrad Hospital for the second time due to recurrences of two skin tumors in the head area. His first visit was in November 2022 when the two skin lesions were excised. One presented clinically as ulceration of the auricle near the external auditory canal, and morphologically as verrucous carcinoma. The second clinically as a nodular skin formation at the tip of the hair follicle, and was biopsy diagnosed as keratoacanthoma.

From the current clinical status: Recurrence of skin lesion #1: Ulcerated area of the external ear, adjacent to the external auditory canal: Verrucous carcinoma. Recurrence of skin lesion #2: Elevated skin tumor at the tip of the hair follicle: Keratoacanthoma.

Material and methods

The histologic specimens were made with fixation of 10% neutral formalin and embedded in paraffin. The cut sections were 4 mkm thick and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (HE).

Result of the biopsy examination of recurrences

Material No. 1: 440-441 / 10.07.25 - Material from the auricle, with the presence of verrucous carcinoma, infiltrating the hypodermis and skin adnexa,

without invasion into the cartilage, excised in healthy (Fig.1 and fig.2).

Fig. 1. Verrucous carcinoma of the auricle, with nested structure and lymphocytic inflammatory infiltration in the stroma - magn.x40.

Fig. 2. Verrucous carcinoma of the auricle with papillary structure and areas of keratinization - magn.x40

Against the background of pronounced cellular atypia and the morphology of a malignant epidermal tumor, there is a papillary and nested structure, hyperkeratosis and stromal lymphocytic inflammatory infiltration.

Material No. 2: B No. 442 /10.07.25 - Keratoacanthoma (well differentiated squamous cell carcinoma), excised in healthy.

Fig. 3. Keratoacanthoma of the capillitium - magn.x40

Fig. 4. Keratoacanthoma of the capillitium with keratinization (bottom left), cytoplasmic and nuclear changes in the tumor cells - magn.x40

Keratoacanthoma also has the morphological characteristics of a malignant epidermal tumor, with hyperkeratosis and nested structure, but the basis for the diagnosis is the presence of areas with optically empty, “glassy” cytoplasm of some of the tumor cells, as well as the multiple pyknotic nuclei, suggesting potential regression of this tumor, which is typical for its third clinical stage (Fig. 4).

Discussion

The coding of these two skin tumors by WHO has changed frequently over the years. For example, keratoacanthoma in ICD-O is 8071/3 - keratoacanthoma, NOS; in ICD-10 it is L85.8 - other specified epidermal

thickening, and in ICD-11 it is 2F72 - neoplasms of uncertain behavior of skin. In ICD 10, verrucous carcinoma is C44: subtype of squamous carcinoma. In WHO (2022), ICD-11, Keratoacanthoma (2C31.1) and verrucous carcinoma (2C31.0) are positioned in the group of Epidermal carcinomas. While keratoacanthoma forms an independent subgroup with its own variants, verrucous carcinoma falls into another subgroup - squamous carcinomas. An important change is mentioned that Keratoacanthoma is separated from squamous cell carcinoma, although it is recognized that it may be a well differentiated squamous cell carcinoma, with a tendency to self-heal [12].

Table 1.

Comparison of Verrucous Carcinoma and Keratoacanthoma.

Tumor	Verrucous carcinoma (Ackerman's tumor)	Keratoacanthoma
Criteria		
Type of tumor	Well differentiated squamous cell carcinoma	
Epidemiology	Average 50 - 70 years old	
Location	Skin and mucous membranes	Follicular infundibulum
Etiology	Chronic inflammation, Repetitive trauma, Scars	Chronic sun (UV) damage
Growth	Slow, exophytic	Fast, endophytic / exophytic
Gross description	Verrucous hyperkeratotic lesion or cyst	Dome-shaped tumor with central keratin plug
Cytological parameters	Unclear	
Destructiveness	Yes	No
Typical localization	Oral cavity, legs	Head, neck, limbs
Clinical stages	No	Yes
Differential diagnosis	Benign squamous cell lesions	Verrucous carcinoma
Recurrences	High percentage	Low percentage
Progression	Yes, after radiotherapy or chemotherapy	No, self-limiting proliferation
Prognosis	Good - skin, bad - mucous membranes	Good, spontaneously regresses

Fragmented biopsy material or incisional biopsy make morphological diagnosis extremely difficult due to unclear cytological parameters in verrucous carcinoma and keratoacanthoma (Table 1). The microscopic features of cellular atypia in these two well differentiated squamous cell carcinomas are almost completely identical (Figs. 1, 2, 3, 4).

Frequent regrouping and changing places of nosological entities in the WHO classifications of non-melanocytic skin tumors may lead to inaccurate diagnosis and subsequent mistreatment of lesions in the spectrum of low-grade variants of squamous cell carcinomas [12]. In this context, a similar study was performed to measure the variability in diagnoses of different pathologists diagnosing precancerous squamous cell lesions and to assess the impact of the diverse terminology on the understanding, interpretation and subsequent treatment planning. This study demonstrated a lack of uniform terminology and diagnostic criteria. The authors recommend the adoption of standardized criteria and terminology to assist pathologists and clinicians in the diagnosis and treatment of precancerous lesions. The classification of dysplasia has also been criticized for its lack of reproducibility and poor prognostic value, but since the classification is based on architectural and cytological changes, there may be significant variability between pathologists' interpretations due to subjective impressions [8]. The degree of agreement between different pathologists classifying dysplasia in the same patients was also investigated, with the aim of reviewing the existing classification system. Histological slides were examined by different pathologists using the WHO and binary classification systems. Statistical analysis showed low interobserver variability with P values of 0.8 using the WHO classification and 0.3 using the binary classification. The study provides evidence that existing dysplasia classification systems are not able to eliminate subjectivity. A classification system that can overcome this shortcoming is needed [6, 7].

Other authors discuss a rare plantar mass on the right foot of a 75-year-old woman that was initially diagnosed as keratoacanthoma but subsequently recurred and discuss the difficulties in both clinical and microscopic differentiation [5]. Keratoacanthoma can be difficult to distinguish from verrucous carcinoma both clinically and microscopically [9]. Misdiagnosis by biopsy may lead to inappropriate treatment. Cases of verrucous carcinoma arising in the parenchyma of a giant keratoacanthoma have also been described [3]. Excisional biopsy remains critical for definitive diagnosis, and it is essential to ensure adequate margins for surgical removal. Keratoacanthoma is often misdiagnosed due to its variable morphology, especially since it is usually single, but can also manifest as multiple tumors [10]. The difficulties in differentiating keratoacanthoma from verrucous carcinoma are well known, necessitating careful pathological analysis [11]. Even IHC staining (Laminin-322) cannot definitively differentiate the two tumors. Moreover, it is important to note that no IHC stain can definitively differentiate keratoacanthoma from verrucous carcinoma [4]. Even the use of a combination of a large set of markers (BDCA2, IL-27, TUNEL, Ley, Cyclin A, Cyclin B, P2X7, p50, E-cadherin, Cortactin, Lectin, and Syndecan-1) cannot guarantee an accurate diagnosis. Although significant progress has been made in the genetic and molecular profiling of these tumors, their clinical and histological features still remain at the forefront of their identification [2].

Conclusions

1. Due to the lack of clear microscopic (cytological) criteria for the histological verification of low-grade malignant squamous lesions, it is essential for an accurate morphological diagnosis to obtain the material by excisional biopsy. This allows for an assessment of the overall structure of the tumor, which is impossible with incisional and superficial biopsy materials.

2. In verrucous carcinoma and keratoacanthoma, the correct diagnosis is more easily made at low power

magnification, because this allows clear visualization of the histological architecture of the lesion, which has a greater diagnostic value than the cytological features of the tumor cells.

3. During microscopic examination, in support of the diagnosis of keratoacanthoma entering a stage of regression, in addition to the accepted morphological criteria (glassy cytoplasm of the tumor cells, epidermal atrophy, dermal inflammation and fibrosis at the periphery), it is also appropriate to take into account the presence of multiple pyknotic nuclei, which are a sign of cell death and tumor involution.

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